

Virtualizing Project-Based Learning: an abrupt adaptation of active learning due to the COVID-19 pandemic with promising outcomes

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Abstract

Project-Based Learning (PBL) is renowned as an active-learning practice that promotes the application of knowledge build-up through real-world and often open-ended problems. PBL has been applied as a methodology at the Engineering School of Lorena, at the University of São Paulo, through different courses over the curriculum of a typical Industrial Engineering student. The first of which is taken during their first semester, in which students must develop solutions for a given single problem through the weekly class meetings. The observations of the evolution of the activities throughout the years demonstrate that the collaborative and group activities act as exercises that develop transversal skills an engineer should possess. These courses have been applied since 2013 under continuous improvements through feedback from the many shareholders the courses present, including the students, instructors, and guest evaluators. The projects are mostly related to the Sustainable Development Goals for 2030. In a matter of a few weeks of classes in 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic forced a quick virtualization of the learning process, posing an unprecedented scenario for the students and the instructors regarding in special this course, which is based primarily on presential discussions and activities. The first weeks of class following the abrupt virtualization of activities were encountered with misinformation and lack of clarity on the adaptation of the activities. Fortunately, through rapid iterations, the adjustment process resulted in time invested by the students and classes with active discussion using the tools made available by the University. In this sense, this work aims to present the forced abrupt changes applied to this first semester course, highlighting the challenges faced and the positive outcomes obtained and observed by both the students and the instructor, making a comparison with the evolution of the course over the past years.

Keywords: COVID-19; Project-Based Learning; Virtualization.

1 Introduction

The challenges involving in recreating novel and adaptable strategies in the training the future generations of engineers often converge to the pathways leading to the roles of each participant in the classroom. The long-standing tradition of passive-oriented courses, with a unidirectional flow of knowledge, coming from the active agent in the classroom, i.e., the instructor, reaching the learners, standing as passive receptors of information is often regarded as a method that often fail to meet the majority of the objectives related to the learning process (Al-Zahrani, 2015). Among the strategies to overcome the obstacles to which traditional Engineering education is set, some active-learning strategies have been developed over the past decades with the main goal of transferring the flow of information within a classroom setting (Hartikainen et al., 2019). These methodologies address the students as the main characters, i.e., as active agents, of the learning process, making them responsible for gathering and working the process to build up knowledge.

The use of Project-Based Learning (PBL) as a practice to promote active-learning experiences has been built upon a wide array of successful cases based on real-world and challenging situations for both the students and the instructors. Since 2013, the Engineering School of Lorena at the University of São Paulo, Brazil, has been offering some courses with primarily teaching and learning practices based on PBL (Pereira et al., 2017). The career in Industrial Engineering at the same program, for instance, has three mandatory courses that students must take on their first, fourth, and seventh semesters of their twelve-semester program that are entirely based on PBL and aim to promote their learning through the development and prototyping of solutions for complex problems through the weekly class meetings. The evolution of the activities, coupled with the

lessons learned over this eight-year frame, have led to some early conclusions that the learning of techniques and concepts that are directly related to the main technical competences one could expect from an industrial engineer is successful. Furthermore, our findings also demonstrate that the application of PBL in these courses served as a strong catalyst in the enhancement of transversal competences to the students, which often are disregarded, or at least not directly evaluated, in a traditional and passive-learning classroom experience.

These mandatory PBL courses are named Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering (IPIE) and are divided according to the technical complexity regarding the Industrial Engineering tools one should expect from a student at a given point in their curriculum. The first IPIE course, offered to first-semester students, is offered as an introduction to the methodology and its problem scope has been, over the last years, been based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) for the year 2030, set by the United Nations. The projects developed by the first-semester students are, thus, often not strictly related to complex Industrial Engineering practices, but rather to diverse settings a typical freshman student can solve building up from previous experiences. Over the past years, a portfolio of IPIE projects were developed aiming to promote solutions to the matrices of renewable energy, to engaging youth in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) practices, and more recently, in 2020, to promote solutions for the challenges of promoting accessible and effective education to children in school years in Brazil.

The calendar of Academic activities in Brazil typically starts off in late February and run for 15 weeks. In a matter of a few weeks of classes in 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic forced a quick virtualization of the learning process, posing an unprecedented scenario for the students and the instructors regarding in special this course, which is based primarily on presential discussions and activities that were not though prior that could be moved to a virtual setting. Fortunately, the adaptation of the classroom activities promoted results that demonstrated more time invested by the students and classes with active discussion using the tools made available by the University. In this sense, this article aims to demonstrate the forced abrupt changes applied to the PBL-intensive course of IPIE at the Engineering School of Lorena, illustrating the challenges faced and the positive outcomes obtained and observed by both the students and the instructor, making a comparison with the evolution of the course over the past years. Our findings, while still in the shadow of the uncertainties caused by the pandemics, are hoped to demonstrate some lessons learned for the years to come and the adaptation of online spaces of learning applied to courses that were not traditionally designed to be virtualized, hoping that the findings and the challenges could yield valuable references for the future learners and teachers in the post-COVID-19 era in Engineering education.

2 Scope and Research Methodology

The research method applied was the case study analysis. This qualitative method has an induction approach on the analysis of data and focuses on the description of the results and their meaning (Voss et al., 2002). The case study approach has an empirical approach, as this method approaches the investigation of a real phenomenon within the context of the real world, often considering the boundaries between the phenomena and the context are not clearly defined.

2.1 Structure, scope, and milestones of IPIE 1

IPIE 1 is taught for first-semester students enrolled at the Industrial Engineering program at the Engineering School of Lorena. Its structure is based on a 15-week semester with weekly meetings of 100 minutes each. The coursework from previous years, i.e., from 2013 until 2019, was entirely based in face-to-face meetings, while just the first two classes followed the in-person based structure. The structure of the first class was divided into segments dedicated to the introduction of the course and the division of the students into teams. Students were classified according to their academic experience, i.e., the students that had already been enrolled in other higher education courses, regardless of the career, were grouped separately from those that have never been part of any higher education activity, reaching a balance of two groups within the first classification and six within the latter. The first class was also useful for the students to know their group and to first familiarize with the theme of the projects for the semester session, which was based on the fourth Sustainable Development Goal, Quality Education. The instructor introduced the need to develop solutions to the problems

facing the educational needs of Brazil, and later introduced the syllabus and the expected deliveries from the students during the coursework. The first of which was the concept of the project each group would be working at, which was presented in the second week of classes. Each presentation lasted for approximately five minutes, which was followed by feedback from the instructor. The third week of classes, following what was planned on the syllabus, did not occur, as it matched with the declaration of COVID-19 having reached a pandemic situation, which resulted in immediate response from the University to shut all in-person programs.

The virtualization occurred starting from an adjustment to the program at the fourth week of classes, using the Google Meet platform. The third class revolved within the theme of project management, which was introduced through Project Model Canvas by the instructor. The thirty-minute theoretical and practical exposition was followed by private meetings from each group using the virtual room setting of the learning platform. The following week was based on a similar structure but focused on the development of a research project. The expectations of the instructor were for the students to deliver a research project on the fifth class. The fifth encounter had as introductory framework the importance of teamwork, which was conducted by an external guest. The students were expected to deliver some tasks aimed at a better understanding of teamwork and how relevant this skill is to the project development. The sixth and seventh classes were dedicated to design thinking, also hosted by a guest, while the eighth class focused on oral and written communication skills. The eighth class was also the deadline in which the students had to deliver their preliminary report, in which they had to describe the prototype of what they were building in their projects. This was followed by the delivery of the prototype at the ninth class through a five-minute presentation, which was examined by four professors who were invited to serve as evaluators in this class.

The tenth and eleventh classes aimed at introducing the students to the norms of scientific writing. In the twelfth class, six students who were in their last year of studies gave a short presentation, allowing a roundtable discussion regarding some expectations of the first-year students. The thirteenth and fourteenth classes were based on meetings and feedback from the instructor, aiming at solving point issues in the projects that were supposed to be presented on the fifteenth class. The last week of classes was hosted by the instructor, having six professors serving as evaluators of each project.

2.2 Data collection

The data collection for the study was conducted via a questionnaire analysis on the last week of classes, through the analysis of the work reports, and through point observations of the instructor and other stakeholders that are not part of the members of the student groups working in the projects. The data collection from these multiple evidence and focal points allowed us the use of the triangulation technique, which consists of the analysis between the different data points. The triangulation of the data allows the visualization of possible converging and diverging points and opens the possibility of integrating quantitative points to qualitative data, and vice versa, according to Flick (2005).

The questionnaire contained a total of 28 questions based on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 (Strongly disagree), 2 (partially disagree), 3 (Neither disagree - nor agree), 4 (partially agree) and 5 (Totally agree), followed by an open-ended question aimed at a general feedback for the course (Table 1). Each questionnaire was answered individually.

Table 1. Questionnaire used at the last class of the IPIE 1 course in 2020.

Category	Question ID	Question
PBL	1	The use of PBL was a differential to IPIE1
	2	PBL concepts should be applied in other courses of my career
	3	The use of PBL methodology made my learning more motivating.
Teamwork	4	The team was able to properly assess the different points of view about the project.
	5	The team was agile in making decisions.

	6	My team researched about the project's theme in the most varied sources.
	7	The role of each member of the team was well defined and everyone worked in their proper roles.
	8	My team knew how to manage time well and fulfilled the proposed schedule.
	9	Everyone on my team was very understanding about the different ideas that come up in the execution of the project.
	10	All members of my team have shown themselves responsible for carrying out all the tasks assigned to them.
	11	My team's success was a function of the cooperation of all its members.
	12	The execution of the project improved the development of the interpersonal relationships of everyone on the team.
	13	All conflicts experienced by the group were overcome in a coherent and respectful manner.
	14	I realize that I learned to seek innovative solutions.
Personal Development	15	I had the initiative to collaborate with the team, even when I was not asked to do it by the leader.
	16	I realize that I have a greater critical sense that helps me to evaluate the different work proposals.
	17	I adapted easily with unexpected situations that arose during the execution of the project.
	18	My view on ethics has been improved in this project.
	19	The decisions that were made considered the impact of the project on the people involved.
Communication	20	The group's communication through the communication protocol was effective.
	21	My written communication evolved due to the project.
	22	My oral communication evolved due to the project.
Integration with other courses	23	I was able to verify a relationship between Calculus I and what I worked on the project.
	24	I was able to verify a relationship between General Chemistry I and General Experimental Chemistry I and what I worked on the project.
	25	I was able to verify a relationship between Reading and Interpreting the Portuguese Language and what I worked on the project.
Leadership and Tutor presence	26	The Tutor participated whenever called by the group.
	27	The contributions made by the Tutor were relevant.
	28	The leader knew how to lead the team very well.

3 Results

Following the assessment of the questionnaire at the end of the first semester of 2020, the quantitative results obtained are summarized in Figure 1. From a visual analysis, it can be observed an overall majority of results within the 4 to 5 range of the Likert scale, i.e., between partially agree and totally agree.

The response of the students regarding the acceptance to the PBL model is totally within the range of partially agree to totally agree, demonstrating that not only the methodology is a differential to the course and that it made their coursework more interesting, but also that PBL should be applied to other courses in their career.

These results, thus, validate the recognition by the students of the importance of PBL to their professional training.

Our assessment also encompassed the evaluation of the perception of the students regarding their responses towards two transversal competences, which were teamwork and personal development, and a technical competence, project management. The analysis of these responses revealed that the students had an overall good reception towards these values, as the majority were between the 4 and 5 range. The two data points with the lowest scores were found in question number 7, regarding the division of roles and the individual contribution to the overall success of the group project. This particular question possibly demonstrated some level of frustration from some team members that likely felt their work was unbalanced towards the average contribution to the objectives of the project. It is interesting to highlight the maturity of the students, especially taking into account that most of them have never been enrolled in a higher education career prior to enrolling to this course. The questions related to personal development were, again, all valued within the 4 to 5 range, demonstrating that the students felt that the methodology and the course project assisted them in building capacities related to creativity, critical sense, and ethics.

Figure 1. Scores of the responses and the range of their 95% confidence level on a 5-point Likert scale (n=40).

Two of the categories that should be carefully inspected herein are those related to leadership and to the integration of the concepts learned in IPIE 1 and other courses from their career, as these had lower scores in the evaluation. Regarding the leadership presence in the group, and the role of a tutor in the group activities, while the average score was within the 4 to 5 range, the confidence level of the range leads to perceptions within the neither agree nor disagree field. Some feedback given by the students in the open feedback question were that one "believes that a greater contact between the team and tutor would be beneficial to verify how the support is being given, and vice versa" and that there should have "more significant tutor presence in the activities". The points related to the integration with other courses were the lowest scored of the overall questionnaire, demonstrating that the students felt that the activities in the course did not converge to the courses in General Chemistry and Calculus 1, which are taken simultaneously, while the course in reading and interpretation of the Portuguese language was higher scored. It is important to highlight that the objectives of the latter are designed to be meant to give the students technical skills to read, to interpretate, and to produce technical texts in an Academic setting.

4 Discussion within the context of the abrupt virtualization

The forced and quick adaptation to the virtual setting of the course was given after two weeks of activities. The students, the tutors, and the instructor alike reached an agreement that the activities would be followed, until further notice, in a mixture of synchronous and asynchronous teaching and working modes. It is noteworthy to acknowledge that, given the circumstances, only seven of the forty open-ended responses mentioned anything related to the virtualization or the effects of the COVID-19 pandemics to the course. Some of these comments include:

“I believe that my experience in this course was complete. There were some limitations regarding virtual learning, nonetheless, the alternatives in which the course work were managed were valid and they led to a full learning experience and to the possibility of the project execution”

“The transfer from the face-to-face to the virtual setting was well executed, and did not lead to significant losses in regard to PBL”

“Even with the setbacks related to the pandemics, I believe the course was well planned and taught”

While there was not any question in the questionnaire evaluating the perception of the students to the adaptation to the virtualization, it can be assumed that, while the process was forced in an abrupt manner, their response to the virtual meetings and to the adapted teaching mode was overall positive. We did not identify any negative feedback that was directly related to the adaptation process, and within a greater context, the instructor and the external stakeholders of the class felt the students were as engaged as, or slightly more engaged, when compared to previous years of the course. Our main assumption to this fact would be that this PBL course was among the few that allowed and encouraged students to actively participate in group discussions. We also relate the evidence regarding the proactivity of some students regarding the submission of the final product as a conference paper, which all were encouraged to be part of, even though it was not a mandatory part of the grading of the course. The students were encouraged to prepare a submission to, and to participate, at COBENGE (*Congresso Brasileiro de Educação em Engenharia*, Brazilian Congress in Engineering Education), taking into consideration that their outcomes were directly related to the implementation or development of technologies, products, or processes in the context of the SDG of Quality Education. We highlight two of these papers herein, which were published at the proceedings of the 48th COBENGE: (i) Youtube Channel to Forward Quality Education in Brazil (Gomes et al., 2020), and (ii) Educational Strategies and their Different Applications as a Complement in promoting Equitable Education (Mateus et al., 2020). Both papers were presented at a national level conference with a focus in Engineering Education, promoting an early entrance of undergraduate students to platforms dedicated to the promotion of science speaking and discussion.

Considering the scope within the classes were to be set, i.e., using virtual meeting platforms, Serhan (2020) demonstrated that the use of video conferencing classes allowed the students to have more flexibility, leading to easier interaction, better written communication, and effective use of multimedia. The same author, on the other hand, cites that the main advantages he found in the survey are related to distractions, to the quality of interaction and feedback, to technical difficulties, and to a poorer education quality. Within our observations, the students were excited to be and to participate in the virtual classroom, and overall lead to projects that were perceived by the instructor and the guest evaluators to be deeper and more complex when compared to previous years. In this sense, we were not able to distinguish the points related to poorer educational quality highlighted by Serhan (2020) given the considerations of this study. The feedback we received had some responses related to some of the advantages highlighted by Serhan (2020), that in this case, overlapped with the perception and the reception of the students to the use of PBL, such as:

“The classes were excellent. The use of PBL went beyond the expectations of what one learns in the course. I improved my proactivity, my communication, my teamwork, and overall, this course capacitated me as a professional and as a person. (...) I wish all the courses were like this.”

“This (virtual learning) experience was unexpected and good for me, considering the pandemic situation. I had the chance to develop some of my abilities, to work in team, and to think outside the box. (The course) was challenging, but with a lot of learning.

Bao (2020) identified five impactful principles for effective teaching practices in online settings. These principles are based on the appropriate balance between an online design and the student learning process, on effective delivery processes of the instructional information, on an adequate support and feedback by the instructors, on effective and in-depth participation of the students in the learning process, and a strong and iterative contingency plan to work around unexpected incidents of online platforms. We believe that part of the promising results obtained at this case study can be related to most, if not all, of these principles. It should be highlighted that the objectives and the operational approaches of this course were not, and will likely not be, related to purely online platforms in the post-pandemic world.

To a larger extent, the replacement of face-to-face learning to virtual practices has been the basis of the emergency adaptation to adapt to the COVID-19 pandemic in many parts of the world, which led to an important debate to be made, based what will happen once we are able to effectively curb the sanitary crisis. While the move to the virtual setting has not been easy, there has been significant investments in overcoming technological barriers to support both students and faculty members. The findings of this work demonstrated that, PBL, given the appropriate conditions, could be adapted to virtual teaching and learning settings. We relate this success to a few points, which are all linked to the context of this study. The first of which being related to the timescale of the group analysis, which was in the first weeks and months of the pandemics, when the uncertain and naïve perception that the perduring effects of social distancing and isolation mechanisms would be, at most, a few months long. This could have caused a positive perception to the adaptation mechanism on behalf of the students, as there was a feeling that they soon would likely be in a physical setting again. The second concerns the size of the group. The student count was of 40 students, which was still appropriate for effective communication and feedback. The structure in which the class was set was transposable to a virtual setting, on a sense that the communication among the students was possibly as effective as when compared to the face-to-face design. The readiness and preparedness of the classroom participants, including the instructor and the students alike, was also a key factor that did not level off the baseline of an effective learning process, as highlighted by feedback comments considering that *“the transfer to the virtual setting was easy and effective, and the process did not leave anything behind”*.

5 Conclusion

Considering all these aspects, our findings are found at an incipient phase of possible hybrid PBL classes in the future, with a few advantages considering the logistics of all the stakeholders involved, including external guests, and the multimedia of online platforms, We believe that, while this course could, theoretically, be converted to a fully online platform, some of the characteristics of face-to-face classroom settings can also benefit the learning and teaching settings, including the ease and rapidness of feedback on group activities, and the overall learning atmosphere of a classroom. In this sense, while this work is drafted still in serious conditions of the pandemics with unclear positions from the future of the classroom, we indicate that the valuable learning and advancements of PBL practices in a classroom can be adapted, and evolve, following the trends of good teaching and learning practices.

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